

Data Management Plan (DMP)

1. Data collection and documentation

1.1 What data will you collect, observe, generate or reuse

The MaNtiS project consists of five separate working pages, which are represented in the Aims 1-5. Each aim has its own data, therefore in the following we describe the data management for the Aims separately, if applicable. First, salutogenic staffing-sensitive maternal and neonatal outcomes will be identified through published literature. Second, midwifery and nurse staffing patterns of a university hospital in Switzerland will be described based on a four-year period. Third, a causal diagram for each of the salutogenic outcomes will be created. Fourth, salutogenic outcome data will be collected from routine data and electronic health records of birth giving parents and their newborns. Finally, the observational data will be modelled and the effect of staffing on the maternal and neonatal salutogenic outcomes will be determined.

Aim 2 – Midwifery & nurse staffing patterns

Routinely collected health-related data (reuse of data)

- Data coming from the nurse staffing system (PEP®) will contain basic information about the nurses and midwives (qualifications, department and unit of work). There will be time varying information about shift time for each nurse and each day of the 4-year period.
- Data coming from the medical controlling system will contain patient characteristics like admission and discharge characteristics, diagnoses (ICD-10-GM) and treatments (CHOP).
- There will be about 20,000 patients (4-year period, 9,600 birth giving parents, 10,400 newborns)
- There will be about 100 nurses and midwives employed during the 4-year period.
- A codebook for all patient and nurse / midwives' variables will be written.

Aim 4 – Outcomes data collection

Health-related data from electronic health record: (collection of data)

- Data coming from medical controlling system will contain patient characteristics like admission and discharge characteristics, diagnoses (ICD-10-GM) and treatments (CHOP).
- Data coming from the electronic health record (EHR) containing information about medications administered, surveillance data like temperature and glucose levels (newborn) as well as all feeding interventions for the newborn.

Overall

The total data volume to be expected is not possible to estimate due to uncertainties about the salutogenic outcomes and confounding variables that will be measured. Nevertheless, we estimate a total data volume ranging between 1GB and 5 GB.

Roles and responsibilities

PhD student

- Responsible for project data life cycle
- Responsible for project documentation
- Access to MaNtiS folder on research drive (University of Basel, remote only via VPN)
- Access to pseudonymized (Aim 2 and Aim 4) data
- Supervision of master students working with data

Principal investigator

- Supervision of PhD student
- Access to MaNtiS folder on research drive (University of Basel, remote only via VPN)
- Access to pseudonymized (Aim 2 and Aim 4) data

Faculty of Medicine
Department of Public Health

Master students

- No access to MaNtiS folder on research drive
- Access to pseudonymized (Aim 4) data

Study nurse

- No access to MaNtiS folder on research drive
- Access to pseudonymized (Aim 4) data

Data scientist clinical site

- No access to MaNtiS folder on research drive
- Access to all identifiable data (Aim 2, Aim 4)
- Provision of pseudonymised data (Aim 2, Aim 4)
 - o Pseudonymisation of midwives, nurses and patients
 - Holds the key for re-identification
 - o Access to key for re-identification
 - o Will create password protected excel document for re-identification

Data warehouse clinical site

- No access to MaNtiS folder on research drive
- Access to all identifiable data (Aim 2, Aim 4)
- No direct contact between study team and data warehouse team.

1.2 How will the data be collected, observed or generated?

Aim 2 – Midwifery & nurse staffing patterns

Routinely collected health-related data will be generated by the data warehouse team from the clinical site and extracted by a data scientist from the clinical site upon request by the study team. The merging of data from different data sources will be applied by the study team.

Aim 4 – Outcomes data collection

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Overall

Data management is given by the Institute's of Nursing Science infrastructure and its standard operating procedures (SOPs). The project will be organised in a pre-defined folder structure, which will be accompanied by a ReadMe file describing the hierarchy and structure of data (see section 1.3). New versions of documents will be indicated by the current date at the end of the documents name (YYYY-MM-DD). Where data is involved, a document with metadata will be created (see section 1.3).

For the data analysis in R, we will work with projects per research aim and use the version control from git and the closed GitHub repository maintained by the Institute of Nursing Science. This refers only to R scripts, health related data will not be uploaded on GitHub.

1.3 What documentation and metadata will you provide with the data?

Overall

The full documentation is stored in the *MaNtiS* folder at the research drive from the Institute of Nursing Science, which is placed in the servers from the University of Basel. Only the study team that is involved in the MaNtiS project have access to the folder.

There is one project overall ReadMe file containing of 1) general information [title, author, date, project structure], 2) research process and organisation [access, data organisation, dependencies], 3) time plan, 4) planned publications.

Each working package (WP) has two overall files, one ReadMe and one project information. The ReadMe on WP level consists of 1) general information, 2) data organisation on WP level, 3) datasets*, 4) codebooks, 5) data creation, 6) data backup, 7) data processing, 8) data analysis, 9) data sharing, 10) data publication. The project information consists of 1) background, 2) objective, 3) methods, 4) time plan, 5) publication, 6) references.

General information consists of the title, authors, date of collection, and further information. Data organisation presents the naming convention, folder structure, dependencies and a list of other files with documentation. In the data set, we will list of all files with a brief description, methods used to generate data and used software (version and packages). The codebook explains all variables, abbreviations used, formats and handling of missing data. Data creation explains how the data was collected. In data backup, data storage and backup are described. Data processing includes applied methods, used software (version and packages), versioning history and reasons for updates. Data analysis consists of the descriptive and inferential analysis. Data sharing clarifies how data will be made publicly accessible, and which parts of the data. In data publication, the licenses, suggested citation, and links to publications that cite or use the data set are written down.

*For each separate dataset a file with metadata will be added in text format. This will include the title, the creator, date, keywords, brief description, file format, an identifier (for publishable data only), and access rights.

The ReadMe files will ensure that the data is understood by other members of the research team and the analyses will remain reproducible after the project is finished and the data published.

2. Ethics, legal and security issues

2.1 How will ethical issues be addressed and handled?

Aim 2 – Midwifery & nurse staffing patterns

Routinely collected health-related data

- There was a jurisdictional inquiry for the access to routine data [Req-2022-00208].
- All analyses will be conducted with pseudonymized data (see 2.2).

Aim 4 – Outcomes data collection

Health-related data from electronic health record

- For the use of EHR data, there was a submission of the study protocol to the local ethics committee followed by their approval [Req-2024-00300].
- Records will be excluded if there is a denial of general consent.
- All analyses will be conducted with pseudonymized data.

All handling and storing of the data are compliant with the HRA. The University of Basel is in charge of the data and holds the full ownership. Data will be made available anonymized for secondary data analyses within the institute (master theses) only with permission of the clinical partner.

2.2 How will data access and security be managed?

Identifiable information about midwives, nurses and patients always remains onsite (e.g., identifiers, names, birthdates). There will be an excel document with the key to the patient and nurse identifiers. This will be stored password protected and with a backup onsite on SharePoint. Only the data scientist external to the project has access to this document.

Pseudonymization of all routinely collected health-related data will be applied by the data scientist from the clinical site. The excel document will also be created by the data scientist and then sent password protected via a secured data transfer software from the clinical site to the study midwife (for storage see 3.1).

Only pseudonymized data will be shared with master students, who are also employed by the university hospital. The data are stored on the servers from the university hospital. This research drive can only be accessed via VPN and only the study team has access to the specific folder.

2.3 How will you handle copyright and Intellectual Property Rights issues?

The intellectual property rights are held by the University of Basel, which includes all data generated during the MaNtiS project.

To promote unlimited sharing of the fully anonymized quantitative data, the creative commons (CC) license seems to be suitable for data sharing. The Creative Commons Attribution license (CC BY – Attribution) will be used to publish further data. This will only apply under the condition that the clinical site agrees to share the data.

3. Data storage and preservation

3.1 How will your data be stored and backed-up during the research?

Research data, pseudonymized health related data records will be stored and backed-up by the university hospital. Former versions can be retrieved.

- Enterprise storage operated and backed-up by IT services from the university hospital
- R scripts will be backed-up on GitHub (version control with git) in the closed repository
- Servers confirm with HRA

3.2 What is your data preservation plan?

Data will be stored for 10 years at the research drive by the university hospital according to their standard and [SNSF recommendations](#).

Anonymized published data will be made available via the open repository Zenodo.

Unpublished data will be saved in suitable file formats. Data in csv file format, analyses in R scripts and all remaining in open accessible ways.

The excel document with the patient and nurse identifiers is stored at the clinical site as well for 10 years on a SharePoint folder only accessible to the study nurse.

4. Data sharing and reuse

4.1 How and where will the data be shared?

Using Zenodo, the merged anonymized dataset will receive a Digital Objective Identifier (DOI). This DOI will be included in the publication of the referring article to ensure identification and access to any dataset in the publication. This is yet to be confirmed by the clinical site.

The DOI will also be linked to the records in the University's publication repository Edoc. Metadata about datasets will be published on the INS's webpage, to enhance public discoverability. Furthermore, the metadata as well as the DOI will be displayed on the researchers ORCID iDs, to further increase the accessibility of the data.

4.2 Are there any necessary limitations to protect sensitive data?

Restrictions refer to ensuring the anonymity of the patients, nurses and midwives. Original data cannot be published, especially individual patient data that is not possible to be anonymized (e.g., admission date). Data will be shared using the Creative Commons licenses as widely as possible. This is yet to be confirmed by the clinical site.

4.3 All digital repositories I will choose are conform with the FAIR Data Principles.

Yes

4.4 I will choose digital repositories maintained by a non-profit organisation.

Yes